

THE COMMUNICATIVE METHOD IN TEACHING SPEAKING IN ENGLISH

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Abstract

This article describes the applicability of the communicative method to teaching speaking in English as a foreign language. In addition to describing the principles of the communicative method in teaching a foreign language, the conditions necessary for the implementation of foreign language speaking are also presented, the most important of which is the presence of a speech situation serving as a potential stimulus for speaking. The communicative method implies that the process of teaching foreign language speaking is built as a model of the process of communication, which requires modeling the situation as a unit of communication and as a form of its functioning. The article also describes the functions of speech situations and their classification.

Keywords: foreign language, foreign language speaking, communicative method, speech situation.

Introduction

The specifics of teaching a foreign language is teaching methods of speech activity, which is a part of human life in general and is a complex and peculiar phenomenon. Types of speech activity, from a methodological point of view, it is advisable to divide into productive (speaking and writing) and receptive (listening and reading) types. However, the differentiation of types of speech activity is necessary, since each of them is specific and based on its own mechanisms, which must be taken into account in the process of teaching a foreign language, including English.

Each of the types of speech activity is important in the successful mastery of English, nevertheless, in the conditions of modern reality, when it is difficult to find a promising and highly paid job without knowledge of foreign languages, the importance of learning to speak English can hardly be overestimated. Thus, the mastery of communicative competence becomes the leading goal, and oral speech activity in general and speaking as an integral part of it come to the fore.

The social order and the needs of society at different stages of its development determine the direction of development of the methodology of teaching English as a foreign language, including such an aspect as teaching speaking. There are problems that science has to address periodically: even if solved at one stage of its development, they require attention at another. Such a problem is the teaching of English speaking. Despite the fact that considerable experience has been accumulated in this field at the moment, theoretical research and many years of practice as an English teacher show that there is a gap between the purpose of teaching - mastering English as a means of communication - and the nature of academic work, that is, the technology of teaching [10, P. 360]. As a result, in recent decades, it has been customary to contrast traditional foreign language teaching with communicative and intensive methods, including the communicative method that appeared in Britain in the 60-70s of the last century, but has not yet lost its relevance. This method considers language as one of the aspects of human existence and assumes that language learning should reflect and affect this being [8; 258]. There are many different approaches and methods of teaching English, but the communicative method is one of the most popular due to its effectiveness, since it focuses on conversational practice, contributing to the rapid memorization of speech structures and overcoming psychological barriers in communicating in a foreign language [1, P. 160].

Speaking is understood as a type of speech activity through which, together with listening, oral verbal communication is carried out. The conducted research shows that speaking is a complex, internally motivated, strictly organized and active process. The next important element of the psychological content of speaking is its product, namely a speech utterance reflecting the conditions of communication and the characteristics

of the subjects of speaking. The unit of the activity under consideration is a speech action or phrase that expresses a certain opinion and includes thematic and rhematic components, acting as a speech act. Having defined a speech act as a unit of speaking, it is necessary to distinguish the units of learning. Such units can be elements or blocks of the phrase itself, as well as intonation and pronunciation, together also called phonation, and language units.

Learning to speak a foreign language meets a number of difficulties on its way:

- 1)the need to stimulate the student to have a thought - the subject of the statement;
- 2)the need to take into account the peculiarities of thought as a subject of speaking, teaching the means and methods of forming and formulating thoughts;
- 3)the need to define, organize and subordinate all units of speaking in order to teach the expression of a thought that implements a speech act in a foreign language.

According to E. I. Passov, a Russian researcher and developer of the communicative method, the term "communicativeness" implies a speech orientation of the educational process, which consists not so much in the fact that a speech practical goal is pursued, as in the fact that the path to this goal is the very practical use of language. Thus, practical speech orientation becomes not only a goal, but also a means, where both are dialectically interdependent [3, P. 432].

Communicative teaching of foreign languages is of an activity nature. This is explained by the fact that speech activity with this approach contributes to solving the problems of human life in the conditions of "social interaction" of people.

Participants of such communication solve real and close to real tasks with the help of a foreign language.

The communicative method of teaching a foreign language is based on the following principles:

- 1)the principle of functionality (any speech unit has certain speech functions);
- 2)the principle of speech orientation (focus on the practical use of a foreign language through dialog communication);

3)the principle of novelty (constant change in the process of communication of the topic of conversation, conditions, goals, etc., which gives dynamism of speech);

4)the principle of individualization with the leading role of the personal aspect (taking into account the speech abilities and skills of students);

5)the principle of modeling (such a selection of the amount of knowledge that is really necessary for students to effectively learn a foreign language and, consequently, effective communication);

6)the principle of collective interaction;

7)the principle of personal orientation of communication (taking into account personal characteristics such as emotions, life experience, etc. during speech interaction);

8)the principle of situativeness (building speech communication as close to reality as possible) [2, P. 431].

Certain conditions are necessary for the implementation of speaking. E. I. Passov identifies at least five such conditions:

1)the presence of a speech situation that is a potential stimulus to speaking;

2)the presence of knowledge about the volume of speech (about the components of the situation);

3)knowledge of what causes and supports the speaker's thought;

4)attitude to the object of speech, depending on the experience of the subject, his system of views and feelings (the motive of speaking);

5)the presence of the purpose of communicating his thoughts and means of expression (speech skill and its constituent skills).

Based on the above, the process of learning to speak a foreign language should be built from the very beginning as a process of oral-verbal communication, which, in turn, is impossible without a situation. The connection with reality is manifested in the situation through its projection in consciousness. A speech situation is a lack of information that has arisen in the process of communication, subjectively significant for achieving the goal of activity, causing a communicative need that is specified in the motive and meaning of speech actions.

The communicative method assumes that the process of learning to speak a foreign language is built as a model of the communication process, which requires modeling the situation as a unit of communication and as a form of its functioning, while the object of discussion, on the one hand, should be characterized by novelty, informativeness, cognition, and on the other - be associated with the life experience of students, their environment, interests.

The communication situation has the following functions: it can act as a way of forming speech skills, conditions for the development of speech skills, the basis for the selection and organization of speech material, as well as a method of presentation of the material [5, P. 274].

R. P. Milrud offers the following classification of situations of speech communication: 1. The situation of speech action. In the conditions of a properly organized educational speech situation, language tools do not function in isolation, in the form of separate words, expressions, structures, but in meaningful speech units, the content of which is determined by the development of the situation. These speech units are called educational speech actions (URD) [4, P. 130]. Being elementary units of communication, they can verbalize a speech idea in a situation of speech action. Situations of speech action are microsituations that represent fragments of the final speech situation. For their organization, the activity background, or situational plot, is preliminarily determined.

An example of a speech action situation is a situation called "I'm very busy right now", when one of the participants is busy, and the other suggests that he do something else. If you simply refuse, it will not reveal the essence of the speech plan to the end, and the speech reaction will remain formal. It is necessary to explain to students that the meaning of refusing an invitation is in an effort to finish the work that has been started, that is, the selected URDS should include, along with the formulas of refusal, structures with continued present tense, value judgments, and incentive formulas.

2. Adaptive speech situation, which is based on game circumstances, in which the real relationships of participants, their life goals and opportunities, everyday affairs and responsibilities find their specific game continuation.

3. Suggestive speech situation, which is based on the dreams, interests, inclinations of students, the actions of favorite characters in books, films, etc., as well as historical events, actions emotionally perceived by children. The term "suggestive" is used in the sense of "evoking proposed representations". Of particular importance in the organization of suggestive speech situations is the response of students to the proposed plot [6, P. 11].

4. Problematic speech situation. The source of speech-thinking activity in a speech situation is its problematic nature. Problems of various levels arising in the course of the activity direct the development of the speech situation. Its potential is considered exhausted if the problems encountered by the participants have been solved [6, P. 16]. There are two types of

problematic speech situations: problem-practical (if the goal of practical activity is remote, but achievable with the help of speech communication, then the necessary speech situation arises, while its problemativeness is determined by the psychological state of the subjects arising in the process of performing such a joint task that requires the discovery or assimilation of new knowledge); and problem-informative (caused by the deconstruction of the task conditions or the situation of a "gap" in the source data; it is characterized by the presence of alternatives in the methods of action, the discrepancy between the available and required knowledge, as a result of which there is a need for speech communication to solve the problem, that is, the information inequality of participants in such a speech situation is a natural incentive to speak; the preparation of students for this speech situation is to ensure their awareness of the problem under discussion, as well as the individualization of everyone's position in the discussion.

Based on the research conducted by R. P. Milrud, it can be concluded that speech situations make it possible to give the speech of students the character of speech communication, consistently complicate educational and speech actions, and ensure the repeatability of the learned lexical and grammatical material. A speaking person always pursues some goal: to convince the interlocutor, to arouse sympathy, etc. Such goals can be called communicative tasks [7, P. 223]. The purposefulness of oral speech

communication is responsible for solving such tasks. Behind each communicative task that arises in individual speech situations, there is a common goal of speaking as an activity - influencing another in the sense of changing his behavior (speech and non-speech), and not just telling him any information. This shows the power of the impact of speaking, and it also obliges the teacher to teach foreign language speaking in the presence of a communicative task, that is, with the help of situations [9, P. 238].

Conclusion

Consideration of the process of teaching foreign language speaking has shown that its effective flow is facilitated by the use of a communicative method, which, in turn, requires specially created conditions. One of such conditions, without which it is impossible to teach speaking as a means of communication, is the use of speech situations, which makes it possible to give the foreign language speech of students the character of speech communication. Understanding the situation as a lack of information that has arisen in communication, subjectively significant for achieving the goal of the activity, makes it possible to model it in the educational process, creating conditions adequate to speech, and thus manage the process of learning foreign language speaking. It is necessary to note the advantages of the communicative method of teaching foreign languages. These include: immersion in the language environment of the language being studied, which allows you to expand and activate the vocabulary, to master not individual words (as with the traditional method of learning), but immediately phrases suitable for various conditions of conversation; the formation of competent, fluent and confident conversational speech in a foreign language, the skill of communication in a foreign language; conducting classes in an interesting way using a variety of game techniques and based on topics that can arouse the interest of students, which gives an additional incentive to learn a foreign language.

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